

Obstructive Sleep Apnea

Shipra¹
Mohd Gulfan²
Shehla Rafique³
Ruchi Saini⁴

Intern¹
Department of Orthodontics
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Intern²
Department of Orthodontics
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Assistant Professor³
Department of Orthodontics
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Associate Professor⁴
Department of Orthodontics
Subharti Dental College & Hospital
Meerut

Submitted 25 February 2026
Accepted 19 March 2026
Published 12 June 2026

Access this article online
Website : www.updent.in
DOI
Quick Response Code

Abstract

- OSA is a complex disorder characterized by recurrent episodes of partial or complete collapse of the upper airway during sleep, causing oxygen desaturation or sleep arousal lasting for a minimum of 10 seconds.
- It is associated with loud & disruptive snoring, witnessed gasps, excessive daytime sleepiness, stroke, hypertension, and coronary artery disease.
- The prevalence is increased with time & age. OSA was reported in 37% of males and 50% of females. And with increasing age and obesity, OSA is more common in males than in females.
- The Diagnostic modalities for the OSA includes MRI, CBCT, CT and radiographic diagnosis such as cephalometry but the gold standard for OSA is Polysomnography.
- With their expertise and knowledge regarding growth and development of oro-facial and dentofacial structures, as well as orthopedic and orthodontic surgical correction of the jaws and supporting tissues, Orthodontics Plays a vital role for the treatment of OSA.

Keywords: OSA, Polysomnography, Obesity, Snoring, Orthodontics, Airway

Introduction

OSA is characterized by recurrent episodes of complete (Apnea) or partial (Hypopnea) collapse of the upper airway leads to oxygen desaturation or arousal from sleep.^[1]

Symptoms which is associated with the term "Pickwickian Syndrome" was recognised over 2000 yrs ago.^[2]

The primary epidemiologic risk factor for OSA is obesity which significantly affects CVS, behavioral conditions, and quality of life.^{[3][4]}

Accumulation of adipose tissue around neck circumference are strong indicators of OSA.^[3]

Individuals with OSA may present with fatigue, nocturnal symptoms & day time drowsiness, insomnia, or morning headaches.^[5]

The Apnea Hypopnea Index (AHI) quantifies severity by the number of apnea and hypopnea events per hour of sleep and these episodes are linked to low blood oxygen saturation or drowsiness, affecting the quality of life and increasing the risk of RTA.^{[6][7]}

The Diagnostic modalities for the OSA includes MRI, CBCT, CT and cephalometry .

and the additional diagnostic techniques include assessment of nasal airflow, respiratory efficiency and oxygen desaturation during sleep.^{[3][6]}

Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP) is the gold standard for OSA.

Definition

Obstructive sleep apnea is a common sleep related breathing disorder characterized by repeated episodes of partial or complete obstruction of the upper airway during sleep which occurs when the muscles

How to Cite This Article : Shipra et al. -

supporting the soft tissues in the throat temporarily relax or collapsed, leads to apnea and hypopneas, which typically lasts for 10 sec.⁽⁹⁾

Prevalence

- In India, estimated prevalence is 11%, with 14% in males and 6% in females.
- OSA can occur at any age but is more common in men.
- Prevalence: 25–30% in men and 9–17% in women.⁽¹⁰⁾
- Prevalence increases with age, especially above 50 years.
- Associated with rising obesity rates ranging from 14% to 55%.⁽¹⁰⁾

Risk Factors

These can be categorized into⁽¹¹⁾

1. Non-anatomical risk factors.
2. Anatomical risk factors.
3. Additional risk factors
4. Associated medical disorders. Major Risk Factors includes,
 - Advanced age (>65 years)
 - Male gender
 - Obesity

1. Non-anatomical risk factors Age

Lengthening of the soft palate, structural airway changes, and fat deposition in the parapharyngeal area increase OSA occurrence in elderly people.

Gender

Men are more likely to have OSA than women due to increased fat deposition around the pharyngeal airway.

Obesity

Increased body and pharyngeal adiposity predisposes to upper airway blockage during sleep.

2. Anatomical Risk Factors⁽¹¹⁾

- Macroglossia
- Enlarged soft palate
- Inferiorly positioned hyoid bone
- Micrognathia and retrognathia
- Facial elongation
- Mandibular hypoplasia
- Adenoid and tonsillar hypertrophy

3. Additional Risk Factors⁽¹¹⁾

- Alcohol and tobacco use
- Use of sedatives and hypnotics
- Smoking

4. Associated Medical Disorders

- Endocrine: Diabetes mellitus, metabolic syndrome, acromegaly, hypothyroidism⁽¹²⁾
- Neurological: Stroke, spinal cord injury, myasthenia gravis⁽¹³⁾
- Down syndrome⁽¹⁴⁾
- Congestive heart failure⁽¹⁵⁾
- Atrial fibrillation⁽¹⁶⁾
- Obesity hypoventilation syndrome

Signs and Symptoms

Nocturnal Symptoms (Fragmentation of sleep)⁽³⁾⁽⁷⁾⁽¹⁷⁾

- Loud and chronic snoring.
- Narrow airway causing airflow

Limitation and turbulence

- Increased body weight, nasal
- Obstruction, intake of muscle relaxants, high BP, night sweating.
- Intensify OSA Snoring is highly prevalent: 25–30% in women and 40–45% in men

Day time Symptoms (Day time drowsiness)⁽³⁾⁽⁷⁾⁽¹⁷⁾

- Day time sleeping
- Fatigue
- Memory loss Mood swings
- Concentration difficulties Morning headaches
- Sore throat
- Decreased libido
- Awakening with sore throat or dry tongue

Diagnosis

A patient with OSA can be diagnosed using:

1. Polysomnography (Gold Standard)

- Records body movements and physiological functions during sleep.
- Determines Apnea–Hypopnea Index (AHI) with severity of OSA.

AHI Grading⁽¹⁸⁾

Severity	AHI
Mild	5–14/hr
Moderate	15–30/hr
Severe	>30/hr
Very Severe	>40/hr

2. Home Sleep Apnea Test⁽¹⁷⁾

- Uses Mallampati score
- Higher score = higher severity
- Score 3–4 → High risk

3. Questionnaire - Based Screening.⁽¹⁹⁾

- ESS (Epworth Sleepiness Scale)
- Berlin Questionnaire
- STOP-BANG

1 Epworth Sleepiness Scale.⁽¹⁹⁾

- It contains a set of simple questions regarding the patient's drowsiness onset.
- The patient responds by grading from 0 to 3:

Score Meaning

- 0 Never
- 1 Rare
- 2 Moderate
- 3 Frequent
- The total score can range from 0 to 24.

- It is recommended that the patient seeks advice from a specialist if the score is >10.

2 Berlin Questionnaire.⁽¹⁹⁾

- It rates the patient's life quality.
- It contains 10 questions divided into three categories:

1. Snoring
2. Daily Drowsiness
3. Presence of Obesity or Hypertension

3 STOP Bang Questionnaire.⁽¹⁹⁾

- It encompasses 4 (Yes/No) questions, based on its acronym:

Acronym Criteria

- S Snoring
- T Tiredness
- O Observed pauses in breathing
- P High Blood Pressure

• A score ≥ 3 indicates an intermediate to high risk of Obstructive Sleep Apnea (OSA). B \rightarrow BMI $> 35 \text{ kg/m}^2$

A \rightarrow Age > 50 years

N \rightarrow Neck circumference ≥ 16 inches in females / ≥ 17 inches in males

G \rightarrow Male gender

- **Low risk of OSA** \rightarrow if the questionnaire has 0–2 “Yes” answers
- **High risk of OSA** \rightarrow if the questionnaire has ≥ 3 “Yes” answers [7]

Other Diagnostic Tools for OSA. (3) Several diagnostic tools are also available for Obstructive Sleep Apnea diagnosis, such as:

- Electroencephalography (EEG)
- Electromyography (EMG)
- Electrocardiography (ECG)
- Electro-oculography (EOG)
- Pulse oximetry
- MRI
- CT Scan

Radiographic Examinations for OSA Diagnosis

Radiographs are very useful in assessing craniofacial structures in OSA patients.

1 Cephalometric Radiography (Lateral cephalogram)

Lateral cephalogram Should be standardized and recorded at the end expiration and not at deglutition because upper airway calibration is affected by respiratory cycle.

Most important cephalometric measurements include:

- **Simple cephalometric analysis for upper airways:**

Parameter	Description	Means values
NAS	Measured from PNS to the upper pharyngeal wall along palatal plane	25.9 \pm 2.6mm (M) 24.1 \pm 2.3 mm(F)
MAS/VAS	Horizontal distance from the tip of the soft palate to pharyngeal wall	9.9 \pm 2.8mm (M) 9.9 \pm 2.4 mm(F)
PAS/ oropharyngeal air space	Horizontal distance from posterior margin of tongue to pharyngeal wall measured on Go–B line	10.1 \pm 3.1mm (M) 10.0 \pm 2.8 mm (F)

HAS	Minimum horizontal distance in hypopharyngeal area measured from point V (intersection of tongue and epiglottis)	18.7 \pm 2.6mm (M) 16.5 \pm 3.1 mm(F)
Hyoid distance	Perpendicular	15mm
(MP - H)	distance from mandibular plane (Go – Gn) to anterior superior aspect of hyoid	
Hyoid angle	Angle from mandibular plane (Go – Gn) to superior aspect of hyoid	25.42 \pm 7.48°

Hyoid, C3 vertebrae and menton relationship	Perpendicular distance from H to line joining inferior - anterior tip of C3 vertebra to menton	Hpoint should be on or above the line
Length of soft palate	Distance from PNS to tip of soft palate	34.3 \pm 3.9mm (M) 30.6 \pm 3.7 mm(F)
Soft palate thickness	Maximum thickness measured perpendicular to PNS – Pline	10.1 \pm 1.4mm (M) 8.9 \pm 1.2 mm(F)
Length of tongue (VT)	Measured from vallecula (V) to tip of tongue (T)	72.0 \pm 4.1mm (M) 64.8 \pm 4.0 mm(F)
Height of tongue	Perpendicular distance from H to VT line (H = highest point on superior tongue surface)	36.9 \pm 3.9mm (M) 32.9 \pm 3.9 mm(F)

Management/Treatment of OSA

- The management of an OSA patient must be carried out by a group of specialists from different healthcare fields, such as: (19)
 - Pulmonology
 - Neurology
 - Cardiology
 - ENT
 - Psychiatry

- Orthodontics/Craniofacial Orthopedics
- Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery
- Treatment can be broadly divided into:⁽²⁰⁾
 1. Behavioural Interventions
 2. Invasive(Surgical)
 3. Non-invasive (Non-surgical)

Behavioural Interventions⁽¹⁸⁾

Patients with OSA are advised to:

- Undergo weight loss
 - Stop smoking
 - Avoid sleeping tablets/sedative drugs as they may worsen OSAHS
- (OSAHS=Obstructive Sleep Apnea Hypopnea Syndrome)

Invasive (Surgical) Treatment⁽¹⁸⁾

This method involves surgical intervention:

→ Uvulopalatopharyngoplasty (UPPP)

- This procedure involves the removal of obstructive tissues in the uvula ,soft palate, pharynx, and tonsils (if present) to widen the airway.
- Maxillo-mandibular Advancement (MMA)
 - Forward advancement of the maxilla and mandible (upto 10–12mm)
 - Helps improve airway patency by bringing forward structures of the tongue
- Genioglossus Advancement
 - Advancement of the genial tubercles and genioglossus muscle to prevent tongue collapse
- Nasal Surgeries o Septoplasty o Turbinectomy
 - Polypectomy

→ These help improve nasal breathing and reduce airway obstruction

Non-Invasive (Non-Surgical) Management⁽¹⁸⁾

a. Lifestyle Modifications

- Weight reduction
- Smoking cessation
- Avoiding alcohol and sedatives

→ These measures help reduce airway obstruction during sleep

b. CPAP Therapy(Gold Standard).⁽¹⁸⁾

- CPAP = Continuous Positive Airway Pressure
- Considered first-line therapy for mild to severe OSA
- Non-invasive, does not require anesthesia
- Delivers continuous positive air pressure via mask to keep the throat open throughout the night
- Recommended for moderate to severe OSA cases
(Acts like a pneumatic splint)

c. Oral Appliances.⁽¹⁸⁾

- Orthodontic appliances that reposition the jaw /tongue
- May be pre-fabricated or custom fabricated
- Useful for mild to moderate OSA or CPAP-intolerant patients
- Orthodontic appliances can be of two types:
 - Fixed appliances
 - Removable appliances
- These appliances bring the mandible and tongue forward and enlarge the upper airway, allowing continuous breathing during sleep.

Examples

- TRD (Tongue Retaining Devices)
- MAA (Mandibular Advancement Appliances)

Side Effects of Oral Appliances

- Excessive salivation
- Mouth dryness
- Headache
- Gum irritation
- Arthralgia(TMJ pain) Teeth pain

d. Positional Therapy⁽²¹⁾

- Aimed at avoiding the supine sleeping position (lying on the back), which worsens airway collapse due to gravity.

Techniques

- Tennis ball technique

→ A small ball is attached on the back of sleep wear to prevent supine position

- Supine alarms
- Positional pillows

e. Medications.⁽³⁾

Used when day time sleepiness persists despite therapy.

Examples:

- Modafinil (Provigil)
- Cephalon
- Frazer
- Solriamfetol

Differential Diagnosis.⁽¹¹⁾

- Asthma
- COPD
- Depression
- Gastroesophageal Reflux
- Hypothyroidism
- Narcolepsy
- Central Sleep Apnea
- Periodic Limb Movement Disorder

Prevention.⁽²²⁾

- Weight loss
- Physical exercise
- Stop smoking
- Stop alcohol consumption
- Oxygen therapy/O₂ consumption control
- Reduction of AHI (Apnea-Hypopnea Index)

Complications.⁽²³⁾

- Hypoxia
- Sympathetic activation Systemic inflammation
- Impaired glucose and lipid metabolism
- Endothelial dysfunction
- Metabolic diseases
- Hypertension
- Cardiac disease
- Coronary Heart Disease(CHD)
- Stroke
- Morbidity and Mortality
- Myocardial Infarction

Conclusion

OSA affects multiple organ systems. OSA may first present with cardiovascular or neurological morbidity, rather than respiratory symptomatology. It is important to use clinical judgement and to keep a low threshold for diagnosis when

patients present with these varied signs and symptoms in order to make a timely diagnosis and to intervene to prevent morbidity and mortality. The untreated sleep apnea on daily activities includes excessive day time sleepiness, impaired cognitive function, mood elevations and personality changes. It is also related with morbidity and mortality. Symptoms of OSA are observed and these disorders need to be treated urgently.⁽¹⁸⁾⁽²⁴⁾

Reference

1. Sankri-Tarbichi AG. Obstructive sleep apnea hypopnea syndrome: etiology and diagnosis. *Avicenna J Med.* 2012 Jan; 2 (1): 3–8.
2. Eos Sleep. A brief history of sleep apnea and sleep apnea signs & symptoms. 2021. Available from: Eos Sleep website.
3. Talera D. Obstructive sleep apnea: clinical overview. Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, People's Dental Academy, People's University, Bhopal (MP), India. *Int J Oral Health Dent.* 2024; Submitted 2024 Apr 1; Accepted 2024 Nov 20; Published 2024 Dec 9.
4. Yeghiazarians Y, Jneid H, Tietjens JR, Redline S, Brown DL, El-Sherif N, et al. Obstructive sleep apnea and cardiovascular disease: a scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Circulation.* 2021 Jul 20; 144 (3): e56–e67.
5. Mirrakhimov AE, Sooronbaev T, Mirrakhimov EM. Prevalence of obstructive sleep apnea in Asian adults: a systematic review of the literature. *BMC Pulm Med.* 2013; 13: 10.
6. Alzahrani MK. Obstructive sleep apnea: epidemiology and clinical impact. Department of Family and Community Medicine, College of Medicine, Majmaah University, Majmaah, Saudi Arabia.
7. Franklin KA, Lindberg E. Obstructive sleep apnea: epidemiology, risk factors and natural history. *Sleep Med Rev.* 2015 Jun; 21: 20–26.
8. Eastwood PR, Malhotra A, Palmer LJ, Kezirian EJ, Horner RL, Ip MS, et al. Obstructive sleep apnoea: from pathogenesis to treatment current controversies and future directions. *Respirology.* 2010 May; 15 (4): 587–595.
9. American Academy of Sleep Medicine; National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (NIH). *Sleep apnea: diagnosis and management guidelines.* Bethesda (MD): NIH; 2020.
10. Peppard PE, Young T, Barnett JH, Palta M, Hagen EW, Hla KM. Increased prevalence of sleep disordered breathing in adults. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2013 May 1; 177 (9): 1006–1014.
11. Slowik JM, Sankari A, Collen JF. Obstructive sleep apnea. *StatPearls [Internet].* Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Mar 4. Available from: National Library of Medicine.
12. Reutrakul S, Mokhlesi B. Obstructive sleep apnea and diabetes: a state-of-the-art review. *Chest.* 2017 Nov; 152 (5): 1070–1086. Akset M, Poppe KG, Kleynen P, Bold I, Bruyneel M. Endocrine disorders in obstructive sleep apnea syndrome: a bidirectional relationship. *Clin Endocrinol*

- (Oxf). 2023 Jan; 98 (1): 3–13.
13. Yaggi H, Mohsenin V. Obstructive sleep apnoea and stroke. *Lancet Neurol.* 2004 Jun; 3 (6): 333–342.
 14. Ilyzer JM, Milczuk HA, Macarthur CJ, King EF, Quintanilla-Dieck L, Lam DJ. Drug induced sleep endoscopy findings in children with obstructive sleep apnea with vs without obesity or Down syndrome. *JAMA Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg.* 2021 Feb; 147(2):175–181.
 15. Sin DD, Fitzgerald F, Parker JD, Newton G, Floras JS, Bradley TD. Risk factors for central and obstructive sleep apnea in patients with congestive heart failure. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 1999 Oct; 160 (4):1101–1106.
 16. Moula AI, Parrini I, Tetta C, Luca F, Parise G, Rao CM, et al. Obstructive sleep apnea and atrial fibrillation. *J Clin Med.* 2022 Feb 25; 11(5):1324.
 17. Johar RA, Aiman R, et al. Obstructive sleep apnea: a review article. *Saudi J Oral Dent Res.* 2021; 6 (5): 221–226.
 18. Agarwal L, Gupta A. Obstructive sleep apnea: orthodontic perspectives. *Int J Oral Health Dent.* 2016 Jul–Sep; 2 (3): 137–142.
 19. Platon AL, Stelea CG, Boisteanu O, Patrascanu E, Zetu IN, Rosu SN, et al. Obstructive sleep apnea: clinical implications and management. *Medicina (Kaunas).* 2023 Aug; 59 (8): 1459.
 20. Cistulli PA, Grunstein RR. Medical devices for the diagnosis and treatment of obstructive sleep apnea. *Expert Rev Med Devices.* 2005; 2 (6): 749–763.
 21. Weaver TE, Calik MW, Farabi SS, Fink AM, Galang-Boquiren MT, Kapella MC, et al. Innovative treatments for adults with obstructive sleep apnea. *Nat Sci Sleep.* 2014; 6: 137–147.
 22. Mayo Clinic. Obstructive sleep apnea diagnosis and treatment [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2021 Apr 13]. Available from: Mayo Clinic website.
 23. Drager LF, Polotsky VY, O'Donnell CP, Cravo SL, Lorenzi-Filho G, Machado BH. Translational approaches to understanding metabolic dysfunction and cardiovascular consequences of obstructive sleep apnea. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol.* 2015 Oct; 309 (7): H1101–H1111.
 24. Sleep Science. Obstructive sleep apnea: recent advances. *Sleep Sci.* 2021 Apr–Jun; 14(2):142–154. doi:10.5935/1984-0063.20200056.